

PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACH TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN FUTURE OFFICERS

Alimardonov Zahid Shukurillaevich

Public Security University of the Republic of Uzbekistan
Head of the department "Educational-psychological provision of service
activities", Ph.D., associate professor

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Abstract

The article provides an analysis of the content, essence and theoretical approaches to the formation of communicative competence in future officers of public security departments. In particular, the issues of interrelation of the concepts of communication, communication, communicative competence, which should be formed in the person of a future officer. Also, the structural features, factors, conditions of communicative competence of future officers of public safety units are indicated.

Key words: future officers of public security units, communication, communication, attitude, communicative competence, personal characteristics of communication, communication, communicative qualities, communicative skills, communicative relationships, individual characteristics of communication, difficulties in communication.

Аннотация. В статье представлен анализ содержания, сущности и теоретических подходов к формированию коммуникативной компетентности у будущих сотрудников органов общественной безопасности. В частности, обсуждаются вопросы взаимосвязи понятий коммуникация, коммуникация, коммуникативная компетентность, которые должны формироваться в лице будущего офицера. Также указаны структурные особенности, факторы, условия коммуникативной компетентности будущих офицеров подразделений общественной безопасности.

Ключевые слова: будущие офицеры подразделений общественной безопасности, общение, общение, отношение, коммуникативная компетентность, личностные характеристики общения, общение, коммуникативные качества, коммуникативные навыки, коммуникативные отношения, индивидуальные особенности общения, трудности в общении.

Collective forms of labor are widely used at the current stage of society's development. In this regard, in the literature, special emphasis is placed on the issues of team management, organization of individual activities, effectiveness of information exchange, and the use of the emotional sphere of interaction. It is impossible to find a solution to these problems without solving the problem of communicative interaction in people. Therefore, in the literature, the main attention is paid to the formation and development of communicative competence of future officers [13].

Much theoretical and empirical material has already been collected in this field. In this process, the answers to the questions about which elements of communication can affect the cooperative activity and what exactly it is, differ with different approaches and perspectives.

Communicativeness of future officers of public security units develops due to their communication skills and is considered a personal characteristic of communication. B.G. Ananyev, B.F. Lomov and T. Shibutani focused on this issue and identified the most general and primary character traits that are the internal basis for the formation of the intellectual, volitional and emotional-motivational characteristics of a future officer [1].

According to the analyzes conducted by N.M. Poluektova and I.V. Yakovleva, communication in social psychology is considered one of the most deeply manifested factors of the individual. In some places, future officers are considered as a mechanism of social self-management. It is known that the term "communication" itself is used in two senses: in a narrow sense - establishing relations and describing their structure (the concept of V.N. Panferov [8]) and in a broad sense - management, information and as a semantic description of relationships, functions, relationships that include emotions (the concept of V.I. Kabrin [7]).

According to approaches to the definition of the term "communication", communicative qualities can be interpreted as a set of characteristics and skills that ensure the ability to relate and understand between people [13].

From this point of view, the concept of "communication" is considered as an integral part of the term "dialogue". Also, this term includes the concept of relations and interaction between future officers of public security units, i.e., perceptive and interactive aspects of communication.

The concept of "communicative qualities" is essentially much broader than "communication" and is used to express its characteristics and is more similar to the term "communication".

In particular, A.A. Bodalyev stated that "communicative qualities" are similar to the concept of "communicative abilities" and include the following: understanding of future officers, adequate attitude to the behavior and behavior of other people, interpersonal relations choosing appropriate communication methods, etc. [2].

Using the concept of "social and communicative skills" by A.A. Leontev, it includes the ability to relate to future officers, the skills of planning and implementing a communication plan [7].

V.N. Panferov, on the basis of "communicative qualities", includes future officers of public security units who express their attitude to people, to themselves, and the process of communication [8].

Thus, all personal characteristics that cover the personal aspect of communication and characterize it as the subject and object of personal relations can be classified as communicative qualities [13].

In this regard, K.K. Platonov also puts forward a unique approach, he says that any psychological substructures of future officers - orientation, character, abilities - can be considered communicative characteristics of a person [10]. Nevertheless, we consider three approaches to the analysis of communicative qualities, i.e., communicative characteristics, communicative relations, and communicative preparation.

The system of communicative characteristics depends on the characteristics of character, temperament, high level of nervous activity, which are manifested in the joint processes of communication and activity (shyness, alienation, neuroticism, autism, changeability, extraversion, etc.).

In the system of communicative relations, it is possible to include relational ties that determine the direction of values and character of communication of the future officer.

The system of communicative preparation includes the knowledge, skills and competencies necessary for organizing interpersonal communication (establishing psychological communication, the ability to predict the behavior of partners, etc.). Therefore, the concept of "communicative qualities" is interpreted

rather broadly and does not adequately reflect the operational characteristics of future officers.

Most of the literature also distinguishes a number of special terms that reflect the content of communicativeness. "Communicativeness" is the presence of communicative qualities in future officers, having a process side of the relationship, ease of communication, freedom, the ability to communicate and establish relationships with other people [7]. "Communicative potential" is the level of development of communicative qualities and the system of skills and individual characteristics that ensure the future officer's participation in the process of communication with other people, his accessibility to the team [12]. "Communicativeness" is the mastery of the social side of the relationship, the ability to communicate [3], etc.

It can be seen from the mentioned points that we were able to consider the related concepts of the main focus on the term communication. From this point of view, it is appropriate for future officers to think about communication skills, i.e. communicative competence. In this process, it is necessary to analyze the pedagogical and psychological factors of the formation of communicative competence in the future officers of the public security departments.

Communicative competence is the ability of future officers of public security units to establish and maintain social and psychological relationships with people. It is known that the concept of communicative competence includes a number of personal characteristics that enable future officers of public security units to successfully solve problems in the process of interaction. In particular, knowledge of social norms that allow to act in the conditions of communicative interaction, communication skills, skills that help to implement the plan of communicative interaction of future officers, behavior that creates a communicative plan. views etc.

According to L.A. Petrovskaya, public security units understand the ability of their future officers to communicate with other people and support them based on their communicative competence. Competence includes a certain set of communicative knowledge and skills that ensure the effective communication process.

L.A. Petrovskaya said that the communicative competence of future officers is determined by the qualities that contribute to the success of the communication process, and the author identifies these qualities with the communicative abilities

of a person [9]. In his research, A.V. Mudrik replaced the concept of "communicative competence" with the concept of "communication competence" and defines it as a set of certain knowledge, social relations, skills and experiences that ensure the effective flow of human communication processes.

E. V. Rudensky defines the communicative competence of future officers as a system of internal reserves of a person necessary for the implementation of effective communicative actions in a wide range of situations of interpersonal relations. These reserves include the cognitive abilities of a person to perceive, evaluate and interpret situations, plan communicative actions of a person in communication with people, rules of behavior management and means of its correction. In turn, communicative correction based on communicative competence is focused on changing the system of value orientations and personal relationships.

Thus, the analysis of the meaning of the concept of "communicative competence" and terms close to it allows to distinguish the following approaches aimed at explaining the essence of "communicative competence". They are interpreted as follows:

- the ability of a person to engage in social relations, to manage repetitive situations of interaction, as well as to achieve communicative goals in interpersonal relations [5];
- formation of interpersonal experience based on socialization and individualization processes [11];
- the ability to engage in communication, based on humanistic personal qualities and taking into account the communicative capabilities of the interlocutor, the ability to appropriately relate to other people at the level of their education and development [4];
- qualities that ensure the success of the communication process (determined by the communicative qualities and abilities of the person) [9];
- systems of communicative actions based on knowledge of communication, which allow free movement and movement in the cognitive world [6].

The development of these aspects serves to develop communicative competence in future officers of public security units.

Based on the above-mentioned points, it is appropriate to put forward the following conclusions regarding the formation of communicative competence in future officers of public security units:

- the formation of communication in the future officers of public security units can be inextricably linked with the surrounding social environment, the human community and the system of interpersonal relations;

- the formation of sociability in the person of the future officer of the public security departments is clearly visible in many ways in their professional activities, future plans, and their relationships with themselves and others;

- it is observed that the formation of communicative competence in the person of the future officer is focused on communicative situations with people, he can easily overcome difficulties in communication and choose a rational way;

- the embodiment of communicative competence as an important factor in effectively overcoming difficulties and obstacles in the communication process in the person of the future officer.

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